

THE EMERGENCE OF GESTURES IN THE FIRST YEAR OF LIFE IN THE
INFANT SCHOOL CLASSROOM

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Abstract:

The psychological literature on the development of gestures during the first year of life has been limited. It has mainly focused on the development of pointing at around 11 months of age, considering it the gesture that allows triadic interactions. However, recent studies have argued for the importance of earlier ostensive gestures (showing and giving), not only as precursors of pointing, but also as important gestures for early cognitive and communicative development. These studies have also emphasized the mediating role of materiality and of others (adults and peers) in communicative acts, especially in pre-verbal interactions. This paper reports a longitudinal study of first year infants in an Infant School classroom in Madrid. Through a microgenetic analysis both infants' gestures and teachers' educational actions related to gesture development were investigated. The results highlight (1) the central role of the teacher in the birth and configuration of infants' gestural repertoire; and (2) materiality as a configurative aspect of communicative interactions during this period as infants communicate not only about objects but through them. Among the types of gestures observed, selfdirected gestures predominated, especially ostensive gestures, these being related to early self-regulation processes. Gesture development could be understood as a process of progressive distancing of the infant from or between the material world and himself/herself. In this process, the teacher can encourage, redirect and structure the infant's productions through adjustment of their educational activity.

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ABSTRACT

The psychological literature on the development of gestures during the first year of life has been limited. It has mainly focused on the development of pointing at around 11 months of age, considering it *the* gesture that allows triadic interactions. However, recent studies have argued for the importance of earlier ostensive gestures (showing and giving), not only as precursors of pointing, but also as important gestures for early cognitive and communicative development. These studies have also emphasized the mediating role of materiality and of others (adults and peers) in communicative acts, especially in pre-verbal interactions. This paper reports a longitudinal study of first year infants in an Infant School classroom in Madrid. Through a microgenetic analysis both infants' gestures and teachers' educational actions related to gesture development were investigated. The results highlight (1) the central role of the teacher in the birth and configuration of infants' gestural repertoire; and (2) materiality as a configurative aspect of communicative interactions during this period as infants communicate not only *about* objects but *through* them. Among the types of gestures observed, self-directed gestures predominated, especially ostensive gestures, these being related to early self-regulation processes. Gesture development could be understood as a process of progressive distancing of the infant from or between the material world and himself/herself. In this process, the teacher can encourage, redirect and structure the infant's productions through adjustment of their educational activity.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In developmental psychology the study of gestures relates to the need to explain the systems of meaning used by human beings to communicate with others and with themselves. Although most of the literature has focused on verbal language as a tool of shared meaning, many investigations have shown the important role played by gestures during exchanges in terms of both, communication *and* cognition (Butterworth, 2003; Goldin-Meadow, 2003; Goldin-Meadow, Zinchenko & Hemani, 2012).

Many definitions of "gestures" in literature, tend to exclude the *materiality* of the communicative act or to give it a secondary role. By materiality we mean the physical context of the interaction, including both manipulable objects *and* surfaces and surroundings. In these definitions it is usual to understand the gesture as being the sign the infant performs with his/her hand and not to include the referenced object. This arises from the view that the "communicative world" and the "physical world" are parallel domains and not inter-related (Goldin-Meadow, 2003; Matsumoto & Hwang, 2013). Some authors have expressed the need to review our concepts of communication and context, because "much of what is currently called *context* is really *acts of communication*" (Clark, 2003, p.244, *our emphasis*). Following this idea, the theoretical-epistemological perspective of the Pragmatics of Objects, which leads the present investigation, considers that human beings do not communicate only *about* objects, but that they frequently communicate *through* them, especially during the first phases of development. Materiality (understood as a complex and cultural reality) constitutes a fundamental aspect of the process in which meanings emerge, as well as in the understanding of the function of gestures (Rodríguez, 2006).

There are other common features in the current research on gesture development: (1) studies have mainly focused on the end of the first year of life when the pointing gesture appears. Pointing has been considered *the* gesture that allows shared reference between the infant and the other (Butterworth, 2003; Tomasello, Carpenter & Liszkowski, 2007). For this reason, the study of distal gestures has been prioritized over the study of proximal ones (Rodríguez, 2006). Similarly, there are more studies focused on gestures directed to others (adults and peers) than those of self-directed gestures, privileging the study of communicative over cognitive functions. (2) Infant's interactions have been considered "dyadic" (infant-object) during most of the first year (Butterworth, 2003; Tomasello et al., 2005) and it is not until 9-11 months old, when the infant begins to use gestures intentionally, that "triadic interactions" (infant-adult-object) begin (Trevorthen, 1990). (3) Gesture investigations have mainly been conducted in laboratories. Due the controlled environment, these contexts do not always enable observation of the pragmatic aspects of gestures and of the role that materiality and adult's educative influence have in the communicative act. Likewise, in laboratory studies the objectives are pre-determined by the experimenter, whereas in the classroom and daily life the infant takes the initiative in producing gestures with significant and functional objectives. And (4) in some studies, gestures tend to be presented as already mature, as if they appeared naturally

at some point of development (Butterworth, 2003; Tomasello et al., 2007). There has been little research looking at possible other processes involved in this development (Carpendale & Carpendale, 2010), such as the educational influence of the adult.

These features lead us to believe that research on gesture development has not sufficiently accounted for gestures that are still immature and in the process of formation in everyday interaction contexts. In response to this situation, the Pragmatics of Objects approach proposes the study of psychological and educational processes as "triadic" from the beginning. This resembles the Vygotskian approach, according to which the adult is the one who introduces the infant into a world of complex practices long before the infant can take the initiative in sharing meanings. (Rodríguez, 2006; Rodríguez et al., 2017).

Recent studies (Dimitrova & Moro, 2012; Reddy, 2008; Palacios & Rodríguez, 2015; Rodríguez, Moreno-Nuñez, Basilio & Sosa, 2015) have shown that there are gestures infants produce before pointing which allow them to establish shared references with others in situations of triadic interaction. Specifically, it has been found that infants from 8/9 months old use objects to communicate through ostensive gestures such as showing and giving (Bates et al., 1975; Cameron-Faulkner, Theakston, Lieven & Tomasello, 2015).

According to Rodríguez (2006), it is appropriate to categorize gestures according to the distance between sign and referent into three types: ostensive, indicative and symbolic. Table 1 shows a summary of the types of gestures that have been identified during the first year of life in recent research. They have been arranged in a theoretical continuum of difficulty given by the distance between sign and referent, going from proximal gestures, through distal gestures, to representational gestures (Rodríguez et al., 2015).

Recent research has also shown that different types of gestures are produced by infants to indicate absent referents, share attitudes, inform, make requests or to ask questions (Liszkowsky, Carpenter & Tomasello, 2007; Southgate, Van Maaen & Csibra, 2007; Tomasello et al., 2007). Infants also produce gestures to communicate with themselves with exploratory and private functions, especially ostensive gestures (Rodríguez, 2009). Private gestures seem to play an important role in the development of early executive functions. In this regard, some authors have provided evidence that gestures could perform early self-regulatory functions (Basilio & Rodríguez, 2011, 2016; Delgado, Gómez & Sarriá, 2010; Moreno-Llanos, 2018; Rodríguez & Palacios, 2007; Rodríguez, Estrada, Moreno-Llanos y De los Reyes, 2017).

Self-regulation through private gestures is understood in situations where the infant has a personal goal about the use of an object but has difficulties in its execution. In these circumstances, the infant proposes his/her own goals and uses semiotic mediators, like private gestures, as "external thinking strategies" to solve the problem he/she is faced with. In accordance with Zimmerman's (2000) definition, self-regulation is conceptualized as a set of thoughts, emotions and actions that infants plan and perform cyclically when encountering difficulties in the use of objects (Basilio & Rodríguez, 2016; Rodríguez et al., 2017). Following

Vygotsky's ideas (1978) (and by analogy with private speech), these gestures arise from the interactions with others. Initially, adults regulate infant's actions using semiotic mediators. Progressively, infants internalize and use these mediators to communicate with others and to regulate themselves.

Table 2 summarizes the different functions of gestures identified during the first year of life, classifying them according to their communicative direction.

Table 1. Gesture types according to the relationship between sign and referent

Relationship with materiality	Gesture Types	Age of Appearance	
		To Self	To Other
Proximal Gestures Communication happens <i>with</i> objects. Sign and referent coincide.	Ostensive gesture The referent occupies the hand. The gesture is made with the same object to which it refers (Rodríguez et al., 2015).	Exploratory functions: 4 months (Moreno-Núñez, Rodríguez & Del Olmo, 2015) Self-regulatory functions: 11 months (Basilio & Rodríguez, 2015; Moreno-Núñez et al., 2015)	Declarative, imperative and interrogative functions: 9 months (Dimitrova, 2012; Reddy, 2008; Palacios & Rodríguez, 2015) Self-regulatory functions: 15 months (Basilio & Rodríguez, 2015; Rodríguez et al., 2017)
	Giving The infant places an object in the other person's space, usually in their hand or lap (Cameron-Faulkner et al., 2015; Moreno-Núñez et al., 2015)	Non-existent	11 months (Cameron-Faulkner et al., 2015; Moreno-Núñez et al., 2015)
	Placing The infant intentionally locates an object in the interactive space in order to facilitate his/her own uses or to share reference (Clark, 2003). It is frequently used by teachers in educational contexts.	8 months (Flores, 2016, unpublished undergraduate dissertation)	Non-documented in infants
	Touching pointing It is half way between an ostensive gesture and point: it is pointing that touches the object (showing less complexity) Infants tend to self-direct in problem solving contexts (Rodríguez & Palacios 2007). Adults use it to transmit their educative intentions to infants, offering a more direct connection with the referent (Rodríguez & Moro, 1998).	9 months (Rodríguez et al., 2015)	Non-documented in infants
Distal Gestures	Reaching	Non-existent (attempts to grasp)	10 months* (Cameron-Faulkner et al., 2015; Leung &

Relationship with materiality	Gesture Types	Age of Appearance	
		To Self	To Other
Communication <i>includes</i> the object but without contact. Distance between sign and referent.	The infant extends his/her arms towards a desired object to request something from another person (Cameron-Faulkner et al., 2015).		Rheingold, 1981).
	Proto-pointing The infant directs his/her semi-opened hand towards an object beyond reach. This is a gesture prior to the consolidation of pointing (Flores, 2016, unpublished undergraduate dissertation).	8 months (Flores, 2016, unpublished undergraduate dissertation)	Non documented
	Pointing The infant extends his/her index finger, with the rest of the hand closed and his/her arm partially or completely extended, in the direction of an interesting object or event. It may be aimed at another person (Butterworth, 2003; Cameron-Faulkner et al., 2015; Carpendale & Carpendale, 2010), or it can be self-directed in contexts of self-regulation.	11 months (Rodríguez et al., 2017).	8/11 months (Cameron-Faulkner et al., 2015; Carpendale & Carpendale, 2010)
Representational gestures The sign represents or replaces an absent object.	Symbols These are the most complex gestures since they imply a degree of absence of the object (Goodwyn, Acredolo & Brown, 2006; Liskowsky, 2007). They can be more or less conventional. For example: clapping to celebrate is more conventional than pretending to turn the lid of a non-existent bottle to express "open the bottle" (Rodríguez, 2009).	11 months (Rodríguez et al., 2017)	11/13 months (Cárdenas, Rodríguez & Palacios, 2014)

Table 2. Infants' communicative direction and functions of gestures

Functions	
Declarative	Gesture to get the adult's attention on something specific in the environment (Bates et al., 1975; Camaioni, 1993).
Imperative	Gesture to demand something from or achieve a change in the environment by the adult (Bates et al., 1975; Camaioni, 1993).
Informative	The infant points to share information that he/she knows that the other is unaware of (Tomasello et al., 2007, Liskowski, Carpenter, Striano & Tomasello, 2006).
To Other	
Interrogative	Pointing (Mintz, Segerdahl and Savage-Rumbaugh, 2007) or ostensive gesture (Moro & Rodríguez, 1991; Rodríguez, 2006; 2007; Sosa, 2010), in order to ask for information or help, requesting the intervention of others (external regulation) in own actions (Rodríguez, 2009).
Fatic	The infant "gives" the object to the other person without any apparent purpose other than maintaining communication (Moreno-Núñez et al., 2015).
Evaluative	The gesture is done after someone performs a successful action (Basilio & Rodríguez, 2011, 2017). For example, lifting an object as if it were a trophy (ostensive gesture) or clapping (symbolic).
To Self	
Exploratory	The infant presents an object to himself/herself in a contemplative way, exploring it, in the absence of later conventional uses (Rodríguez, 2006, Dimitrova & Moro, 2012).

Functions

Gestures produced in problem solving contexts as forms of self-regulation. They are followed by conventional uses of objects or instruments. For example:

Private

- (1) Private ostensive gestures: the infant offers himself/herself a hoop as an object of reflection, to analyze its position, distance and trajectory when placing it on a pivot (Rodríguez & Palacios, 2007).
 - (2) Private pointing: the infant points out the hole where he needs to insert the figure before introducing it, indicating to himself/herself the course of action in a self-declarative way (Basilio & Rodríguez, 2017; Rodríguez et al., 2016). They are also used by infants to direct their attention to an event (Delgado, Gómez & Sarriá, 2006; Español & Rivière, 2000).
 - (3) Private symbolic gestures: the infant applauds after performing a task successfully, evaluating his/her own performance (Basilio & Rodríguez, 2011; Rodríguez, 2009).
 - (4) Private emotional gestures: the infant rotates both hands when the teacher places the spoon in his plate indicating to him to try and use it (Rodríguez et al., 2017).
-

It is important to mention that the lack of inclusion of everyday contexts in research has led to a shortage of literature regarding situations where the adult intentionally communicates with the infant and the influence that this could exert on the origins of infants' gestures. In studies carried out at family homes, it has been shown that parents are important mediators between the infant and the world. They exercise an educational role through different semiotic systems that allow the infant to progressively take ownership of their communicative intentions, until he/she manages to internalize them and to use them autonomously (Cuevas, 2006). If this is the case with parents, it can be assumed that in the Infant School, teachers must multiply or diversify this type of mediation.

According to the statistical data from 2018-2019 of the Community of Madrid, at least 94,490 infants, from 0 to 3 years old, currently attend public Infant Schools. This represents 7.8% of the students enrolled in all the educational system in Madrid (Consejería de Educación e Investigación de la Comunidad de Madrid, 2018). Given these attendance records, research on socio-cognitive development in everyday contexts in early years school, not only has benefits at a theoretical level, but also finds great practical application. Among others, teachers have the fundamental task of creating spaces, situations and interactions that promote the infants' development, providing them with security to explore their abilities and with challenges to make them go forward, taking advantage of the neuropsychological potential present at this stage. Understanding how these interactions work is a task still to be undertaken as there is a notable lack of studies of these processes in the Infant School.

2. METHOD

The present study was conducted in the daily context of an Infant School, aiming to answer two research questions about gesture development during the first year of life:

- What gestures infants do produce in the classroom and how do they develop?
- Could educational action and infants' gesture development be related?

We proposed two working hypotheses:

1. Gestures might appear in infants' development according to their semiotic complexity. Proximal gestures would appear earlier in development, followed by distal gestures and, by the end of the first year, some prototypical forms of symbolic gestures.
2. The relation between the educative action and the infant's gesture development might be found in the teacher's organization of the classroom conditions and materiality. Proximal gestures might be facilitated by activities where the materiality is accessible to the infants, but they might be hindered by activities where materiality is mostly controlled by the teacher. However, these activities of restricted materiality would encourage more distal and symbolic gestures.

For answering the research questions, we selected the Infant School "La Cigüeña María". It is a public institution located in one of the municipalities with the highest annual income of Madrid (Spain), but the infants came from different socioeconomic backgrounds. The school's curriculum and educational program was representative of the current public infant education model in Madrid.

We filmed a full day of activity in the 0-1 year-old classroom, without giving any instructions to the teacher nor providing additional materials. Filming was conducted four times over four months: T1 - October, T2 - November, T3 - December and T4 - January. In total there were 12 videos, classified according to three situations of the day: welcome activity, main activity and mealtime.

The participants were 8 infants (5 boys and 3 girls) and their teacher. The teacher was 39 years old and had 13 years of working experience, with a bachelor's degree in Early Childhood Education. At the beginning of the investigation, the age range of the infants was between 4 months and 11 days, and 8 months and 7 days. At the end of the filming the infants were between 7 months and 18 days, and 11 months and 13 days.

A multivariate and longitudinal design was used, with a descriptive analysis scheme (León & Montero, 2016). The data analysis was executed through qualitative research strategies (description of observations and photographic sequences) and through the located microgenetic behavioral coding method. The microgenetic analysis allows the observation of moment-by-moment change as it occurs in a relatively short span of time for an increased number of events (Siegler, 2006). Observing and comprehending micro-level changes in real time allow us to apprehend macro-level changes on developmental time (Calais, 2008; Siegler, 2006). According to Saada-Robert & Balsley (2006), this method is the only one capable of simultaneously focus on cognitive development and the specific context where it takes place, emphasizing everyday environments.

The analysis was divided into two phases:

2.1. Phase 1. Analysis of the infants' gestures

We performed an exhaustive transcription of the infants' gestures using the ELAN Software [v.4.9.5, 2016]. For each occurrence, we coded using categories derived from previous studies (Cárdenas, Rodríguez & Palacios, 2014; Cavalcante & Rodríguez, 2015; Basilio & Rodríguez, 2011; Rodríguez & Palacios, 2007; Moreno- Núñez, Rodríguez & del Olmo, 2015). These categories are detailed in Table 3.

Table 3. Categories for infants' gesture analysis

SC*	Types of Gesture	To Self	To Other	Function	Referent
Grasping Attempt	Grasping Attempt	✓		Grasping Attempt	
Ostensive Gestures	Showing	✓		Exploratory Private	Materiality included in the communicative act
			✓	Declarative Imperative Interrogative Informative Private	
	Giving		✓	Fatic Private	
	Placing	✓	✓	Private Declarative Imperative Informative Interrogative	
Indicative Gestures	Reaching		✓	Imperative	Materiality included in the communicative act
	Touching Pointing	✓		Exploratory Private	
			✓	Declarative Imperative Informative Interrogative	
	Proto Pointing	✓	✓	Exploratory Private Declarative Imperative Informative Interrogative	
Representational gestures	Symbolic	✓		Private	
			✓	Evaluative Declarative	

*SC: *semiotic complexity*

The “Grasping attempts” category only considered those attempts that received a response from the teacher and therefore showed signs of involving the other. It was distinguished from reaching gestures for its communicative direction, as these are clearly others-directed.

2.2. Phase 2: analysis of the educational action

We understood the “educative action” as the strategies and mediations that teachers execute intentionally in the classroom to achieve specific educational objectives, emphasizing the materiality as a mean of communication, knowledge and socialization (Munch, 2014, Rodríguez *et al.*, 2018). Although these educative objectives do not necessarily relate explicitly to gesture development, we can argue that they are related to the infants’ socio-cognitive development through different semiotic systems. Therefore, we consider the educative action as a fundamental part of the “educative situation” [*situation educative*] as it is defined by Brossard (2001) and Tapparel (2014), where the elements included in it are intentionally planned, organized and put into action according to a set of specific educative objectives.

The categories for analyzing the educational action resulted from the observations (Leon & Montero, 2016). We had two levels of analysis: (1) “Planned Educational Action” and (2) “Immediate Educational Action”. The first refers to an educational ‘proposal’ by the teacher and how it influences the infant’s gestures. The second refers to the *ad hoc* actions carried out by the teacher at the time an infant produces a gesture. Planned educational action includes aspects such as: type of activity, materiality, access that infants have towards objects, and the role of infants and adults in the activity. Immediate educational action develops following the “rules” that were established in the planned educational action, mediating between the infant, his/her circumstances and the educational situation proposed by the teacher.

As planned educational action happens before interacting with the infants, it was analyzed as a global category based on descriptions and an illustrative photographic compilation (Markström & Halldén, 2009, McWilliam, de Kruif & Zulli, 2002, Rodríguez *et al.*, 2017). In contrast, the immediate educational action, observable during the teacher-infant interaction, was codified using the ELAN software according to the categories summarized in Table 4. We started from infant gestures previously identified and then coded the teacher’s actions before, during and after. Three main functions were considered: the teacher performs actions that *promote* gestures, she *accompanies* them by encouraging communication, or she *corrects* them. Interactions that occurred outside the teacher’s educative proposal were excluded from the coding.

Table 4. Functions of the Immediate Educational Action

Function	Semiotic Systems	Examples
<p>Promotion Teacher's (T) intervention that results in an infant gesture.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Verbal language. - Gestures (ostensive gestures, placing, pointing). - Direct actions (changes in position). - Uses of objects (distant and immediate demonstrations). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - T proposes a challenge to the infant by placing an object of interest out of reach. - T verbalizes a future activity that infants are familiar with. - T changes the infant's position to improve his/her access to objects
<p>Accompaniment T's intervention provides the infant's gesture with communicative and contextual meaning.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Verbal Language. - Gestures (ostensive gestures, placing, pointing, symbols). - Direct actions - Uses of objects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - T. verbalizes the function of the infant's gesture "Do you want to give the boat to S?" - The infant points to request, e.g. a piggy-bank outside the educational planning, and T. agrees to this request. - When the infant presents a ball to herself, T. performs a verbal recognition saying, "That's it!".
<p>Correction Intervention of T. that extends, structures or elaborates a gesture that an infant has initiated, making it more complex.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Verbal Language. - Gestures (imitation). - Direct actions (adjustments). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When the infant makes an ambiguous gesture, T. imitates the infant's gesture but in its conventional form. Then the infant repeats the gesture or improves it. - T. motivates the infant to continue with the gesture he is doing by saying "keep going!". - Infant tries to reach for a rattle. T. moves the rattle closer to him so that it is within reach (she intervenes in the environment to adjust the level of difficulty of the challenge).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Phase 1. Analysis of the infants' gestures

From the microgenetic analysis of the videos, 359 gestures were coded in total. The most frequent were ostensive gestures (166), followed by grasping attempts (70), symbols – clapping and greetings (36), pointing (30) and proto-pointing (27). The least frequent were reaching (18), touching pointing (11) and placing (1) (See Fig. 1).

PLEASE INSERT HERE FIGURE 1

Fig. 1 Total of gestures coded

Infants' gestures in the classroom from T1 to T4 do not only increase or decrease in quantity but they also diversify (see Table 5). The gesture repertoire progressively includes more complex and less polysemous ways of expression that gradually separates infants from their immediate environment towards more distant or absent referents. Gestures went from a progressive diminishing of less complex productions, such as grasping attempts and reaching, to an increasing use of more complex ones, especially proto-pointing and pointing (see Fig. 2).

However, throughout the videos ostensive gestures maintained a markedly higher frequency than other types of gestures. They were the only ones observed in all participants, being mostly self-directed and with an exploratory function.

PLEASE INSERT HERE FIGURE 2

Fig. 2. Infants' gesture types from T1 to T4

At T3 (when some participants were 10 months old), initial forms of pointing gestures appeared, such as proto-pointing and touching pointing. Conventional pointing appeared later at T4 (around 11 months old). Gestures of less complex nature (ostensive gestures, touching pointing, proto-pointing) continue to be used after acquiring conventional pointing.

Concerning the communicative direction, self-directed gestures predominated regardless of infants' ages and filming time (see Fig. 3). It was not until 8 months old that infants began to use gestures to communicate with others, especially with their teacher.

PLEASE INSERT HERE FIGURE 3

Fig. 3. Communicative direction of gestures according to infants' age (in months) and filming time.

It was observed that infants' interaction with materiality had a structure. Infants alternated their activity between periods of selection, contemplation through self-directed ostensive gestures, and uses of objects (see Table 6). They would completely stop their activity and produced self-directed ostensive gestures in order to contemplate the properties of the object before returning to its use (Moreno-Llanos, 2016; Rodríguez, 2006). This alternation was only observed when infants interacted with unknown objects. By contrast, with familiar objects infants would make continuous short-term uses with no contemplation periods.

Table 5. Observation 1: Alternation with rattle, can and lid: self-directed ostensive gesture and rhythmic sonorous use

Observation 1. T3 – Welcome Activity		
<i>Participant:</i> P.	<i>Age:</i> 0;9,27	<i>Materiality:</i> Can, lid and rattle
Situation: The teacher places a basket with Christmas objects within the reach of P, who begins to pull them out.		

Observation 1. T3 – Welcome Activity

Participant: P.

Age: 0;9,27

Materiality: Can, lid and rattle

P. takes a can and its lid. She hits them against each other making them make a sound (non-conventional **use**).

P. stops her activity, lets go of the can and presents the lid to herself for 3 seconds (self-directed **ostensive gesture**).

P. shakes the lid up and down, hitting it against the mat to make it make a sound (non-conventional **use**).

She stops and presents the lid to herself, turning it around for 8 seconds (self-directed **ostensive gesture**).

P. releases the can and the lid. She takes the basket and looks for another object.

She **selects** a rattle from the basket and takes it out. P. presents it to herself (self-directed **ostensive gesture**), observing and rotating it for 3 seconds.

P. makes a rhythmic-sonorous use of the rattle (conventional **use**) hitting it against her right hand.

She completely stops her activity and returns to contemplate the rattle (self-directed **ostensive gesture**) for 5 seconds.

Observation 1. T3 – Welcome Activity

Participant: P.

Age: 0;9,27

Materiality: Can, lid and rattle

She continues the rhythmic-sonorous use, shaking the rattle.

The same sequence can be observed throughout the video with 3 different objects that are removed from the basket (necklace, bell and ornaments).

Type of gesture: Ostensive gesture (Showing).
 Communicative direction: Self-directed.
 Function: Exploratory.

3.2. Phase 2: analysis of the educational action

(a) Planned Educational Action

In our analysis of the teachers' educational proposals, one of the most outstanding aspects was the constant change in the material circumstances of the classroom (Moreno-Llanos, 2016). Access to the materiality was carefully planned and reinvented as the school year progressed (see Table 7).

Table 6. Materiality disposition in T1-T4

Classroom T1. Welcome activity – Structured educative situation	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mattresses for easy mobility and protection, promoting infant's autonomy • Mobiles and mirrors at infants' height. • Objects placed by teacher as an educative proposal.
Classroom T4. Welcome activity – Semi-structured educative situation	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility of free mobility throughout the classroom. • Mobiles and images at different heights. • Objects in different formats, e.g. plastic figures of animals, hanging images of snowflakes. • Objects that help reach inaccessible places, e.g. tables.

Given this variability in the classroom conditions, we hypothesized that classroom organization and the object's arrangement would facilitate the appearance of certain gestures

and hinder the performance of others (See Table 8). Therefore, we analyzed the relationship between the accessibility infants had to the materiality during an activity and the gestures they produced:

Table 7. Examples of activities with different materiality accessibility

Materiality: Accessible (Replica-sonorous objects/ Books)
Potential gestures: Proximal (P), Distal (D), Representational (R)

Materiality: Fairly Accessible (plates and spoons)
Potential gestures: P, D, R.

Materiality: Inaccessible (book / puppets)
Potential gestures: D, R.

Regardless of the infant's age, activities with free accessibility to materiality promoted proximal gestures, self and other directed. On the other hand, activities where the infant had restricted access to the materials increased distal and representational gestures (see Fig. 4).

PLEASE INSERT HERE FIGURE 4

Fig. 4 Gesture types according to accessibility to materiality of the activity.

Likewise, accessibility to materiality produced variations in the infants' participation. In activities that allowed free access to materials every infant communicated through gestures. But when the activity didn't allow access to materiality, only the older infants of the group (9 months old at least) participated (see Fig. 5).

PLEASE INSERT HERE FIGURE 5

Fig. 5 Participation in activities: age and accessibility.

(b) Immediate Educational Action

The data indicate that 52% of gestures in the classroom (see Fig. 7) were related to the activity of the teacher (33% of the actions to promote, 13% to accompany and 6% to correct). This implies that the teacher, according to her ways of acting, was able to influence how infants expressed themselves through gestures.

PLEASE INSERT HERE FIGURE 6

Fig. 6 Percentage distribution of the immediate educational action.

The teacher could act before the gesture's occurrence, *promoting* its appearance, or could act after it in two ways: (1) *Correcting* the gesture or (2) *Accompanying* it (see Table 4). In some sequences the same action could have several functions. Also, there could be many actions with different functions for the same gesture. Correcting gestures led to new sequences of educational action/infant gesture, while the accompaniments of these mostly generated isolated sequences.

When promoting, correcting or accompanying gestures, the teacher resorted to different semiotic mediators: language, gestures (ostensive gestures, placing, pointing and symbols), uses of objects (distant or immediate demonstrations of conventional uses) and direct actions (acts directly on the infant's body or on the environment). In addition, she used different techniques that made the semiotic mediator more striking or explicit, such as rhythmic-sonorous components (onomatopoeias, movements or shakes of the object), accompaniment with facial or bodily emotional expressions, and eye contact. These emphatic aspects of the action have been called "redundancies" and are presented both by parents (Rodríguez & Moro, 1998) and teachers.

Educative action was mostly observed in gestures that infants directed to others. However, sometimes the teacher's activity was fundamental in self-directed gestures, such as grasping attempts. Although the infant was concentrated on his/her own activity and objective, the teacher would intervene in various ways (Table 9):

- Promoting: she did not deliver the object directly to the infant but placed it at a distance, challenging him/her to reach for it.
- Accompanying: when observing an attempt to grasp, the teacher placed a hand under the infant's feet so that he could push himself towards the object, thus adjusting the level of difficulty of the challenge.

Table 8. Observation 2: Educative action with self-directed gestures.

Observation 2. T1 - Welcome Activity		
<i>Participants:</i> IIs. and T.	<i>Age:</i> 0;8;5	<i>Materiality:</i> Piggy-bank and tokens
<p>T. proposes a challenge to IIs demonstrating the conventional use of the piggy-bank and tokens: she opens the compartment located in the piggy-bank's belly and puts a token inside (P)</p>		<p>IIs looks with interest. He takes a token and waves arms and feet. T. emphasizes the challenge with a touching pointing to indicate the token that she had placed in the piggy-bank (Redundancy).</p>
<p>There is no apparent answer from IIs. T. reiterates the challenge. She takes the token from IIs. and places it in the piggy-bank (P)</p>		<p>IIs tries to reach the token that T. placed in the piggy-bank. T. says: "A little more, let's go" (C).</p>
<p>IIs manages to reach the token. T. positively evaluates his performance: "Very good!", while she gives him a pat (A).</p>		<p>T. observes that IIs continues making grasping attempts towards the tokens. She places her hand behind IIs's feet to allow him to push himself towards the token (C).</p>
<p>T. Type: Promote (P), Acompany (A), Correct (C) Semiotic mediators: Verbal language, gestures (touching pointing), direct actions. Redundancies: Repeating and emphasising the challenge, moving the tokens.</p>		
<p>IIs. Gestures: Grasping attempt. Communicative direction: Self-directed. Funtion: Grasping attempt.</p>		

We also observed interactions where the teacher corrected the infant's symbolic gestures when they were not performed in conventional ways, seeking to structure or repeat them. She took the infant's initial proposal (used the infant's own objectives on which to base the scaffolding) and imitated it, but in its conventional format (see Table 10).

Table 9. Observation 3: T. corrects infant's ambiguous gestures.

Observation 3. T4 – Main Activity		
<i>Participants:</i> Y. and T.	<i>Age:</i> 0;11,9	<i>Materiality:</i> Theater and puppets
Situation: During the theater, Y. greets one of the puppets.		

Y. greets a puppet (which is off camera) with an ambiguous manual configuration and lateral movements (proto-symbolic form).

T. takes Y's proposal and greets the puppet in a conventional way, saying: "Hello mom!" Y. stares at her (C).

Y. repeats the greeting more slowly, without making progress in its execution. He makes this gesture while looking at the teacher with an apparent interrogative function about the execution itself.

Y. changes his gestures to a point, sharing with T. what has caught his attention. T. continues the interaction by looking where Y pointed to.

T.
 Function of Educative Action: Correct (C)
 Semiotic mediators: language, gestures (symbolic – greet).

Y.
 Gesture Type: Proto-symbolic / Pointing
 Communicative Direction: To others.
 Function: Interrogative / Declarative

It is important to highlight the interrogative function observed in the proto-symbolic gesture of Y, as the infant recognizes that his own performance is not adequate and actively seeks regulation from the teacher (Rodríguez, 2009). These communicative exchanges, where the teacher provides feedback of the infants' gestures, may be scaffolding early self-regulation processes in communicative competences.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Through a microgenetic method we conducted an analysis of infants' gestures in a first year of life classroom of an Infant School in Madrid. As previous research has suggested (Cameron-Faulkner et al., 2015; Carpendale & Carpendale, 2010; Rodríguez et al., 2015, 2017), gesture development can be understood as a process where the infant gradually separates from his/her immediate surroundings, towards distant or absent referents in time and space. The first gestures infants understand and produce are proximal ones (such as ostensive gestures). Progressively, they incorporate distal and representational gestures into their communicative practices. The beginning of this incorporation is at around 8/9 months old, when infants start using reaching, conventional symbols, touching pointing and proto-pointing. The results of this study support the idea that gestures are initially self-directed with mostly exploratory functions. As they develop through triadic interaction, where the adult responds to the infant's expressions and employs different semiotic mediators to communicate, gestures begin to be directed to others in contexts where they are meaningful (Basilio & Rodríguez, 2017).

Ostensive gestures were the most frequently observed and the only ones made by all participants. As previous studies suggest (Nordtomme, 2012; Rodríguez et al., 2015, Rodríguez, 2006), during their first months, infants communicate *with* and *through* objects, endowing the materiality and the educational proposal with a central role in early socio-cognitive development. It can be said that ostensive gestures are one of the first forms of communication that infants have in order to relate to themselves and with others.

Literature that has dealt with cognitive development has emphasized that infants' activity during their first months focuses on an "active exploration" and manipulation of the material world. Our results show that infants do not act on the world in a random way, but that they employ strategies of selection, action (uses) and contemplation (ostensive gestures). This alternation gives an organization and structure to infants' activity which has not been studied before. The fact that these self-directed exploratory ostensive gestures only appeared with novel objects or with objects whose uses were unknown to infants, might be related to the acquisition of knowledge about conventional uses of objects and to the early development of cognitive self-regulation processes. We can affirm that, during the first year of life, ostensive gestures seem to be one of the main forms of communication with oneself, a cognitive instrument and a sign of: (a) interest towards materiality; and (b) the educational potential of the proposal presented by the teacher.

Even though ostensive gestures were the most relevant gesture of our findings, interesting results were also observed in other gestures:

Grasping attempts appeared with high frequency between 4-7 months old. The teacher did not only promote this type of interaction, but also gave them a communicative value, as she also did with conventional gestures. This type of response from the teacher transformed the

dyadic interaction initiated by the infant into a triadic interaction. If these interactive patterns are repeated over time, infants will become increasingly aware of the impact that their activity has on others. This realization might progressively change their self-directed attempts to grasp into other-directed conventional gestures. We suggest that these communicative exchanges where the adult introduces the infant into a triadic interaction by interpreting a seemingly unintentional act as intentional, could be related to the subsequent birth of gestures of greater semiotic complexity, such as pointing or reaching (Vygotsky, 1978, 1988).

We observed previous non-conventional forms of pointing (proto-pointing and touching pointing) from T3 to T4. These forms of shared reference of an indicative nature, prior to the consolidation of conventional pointing, might give us a clue about pointing's origins. It may not develop as a "natural" skill in the infant (Butterworth, 2003; Tomasello et al., 2007), but instead, pointing may go through a process of progressive improvement of motor and cognitive skills through repeated interaction. It requires further specific research on this topic in order to reach clearer conclusions.

Proto-pointing and touching-pointing continued to be used even after infants' had mastered conventional pointing. This indicates that these gestures do not only function as a transition from a proximal to a distant gesture communication, but they could fulfill differential functions. Some studies (Rodríguez, 2006) have observed private touching pointing in problem-solving contexts, where the infant self-directs it as a way of "thinking through the gesture" (early self-regulation). It is also used often by teachers and parents (Basilio & Rodríguez, 2011, 2016; Wu & Gros-Louis, 2014) when they try to reduce ambiguity in the referent identification.

Not every infant produces the same type of gestures, with similar functions in equal situations. An interesting way to continue this research would be to analyze the data from an intra-individual perspective to explore this diversity. For example, even if ostensive gestures were observed in all participants at different ages, we found great diversity in how attractive the materiality was for each infant. These differences might relate to (1) aspects of the materiality, such as its novelty, complexity or ease of handling, (2) aspects of the infant, such as his/her goals related to the use of objects, or (3) aspects of the interaction infant/educative action, such as the requirements of the activity proposed in terms of participation. Likewise, while some infants at 10 months old produced touching-pointing and proto-pointing in their interactions with objects, some others preferred explorations through self-directed ostensive gestures. Further data on the gesture development of each infant through the whole year would be helpful to reach clearer conclusions in these matters.

This research emphasized the work carried out by the Infant School and its potential as a formal educative context for socio-cognitive development. We highlighted the planning of educational situations with the constant reinvention of the classroom materiality throughout the school year. This allows the teacher to adjust to the demands of the diversity of infants and to

structure the classroom as a challenging and welcoming environment, that undoubtedly influences infants' gesture development.

Gesture development and planned educational action are in constant change and mutual adjustment. The teacher adapts her proposals to the level of development of the infants, challenging them to go beyond their current possibilities. Meanwhile, infants progressively become more able to participate in the activities, demanding greater complexity in them and allowing new situations of communicative exchange. Especially during the first months of life, activities of greater contact with materiality seemed to be more accessible for infants, allowing them to participate through less complex gestures (proximal ones). Activities of restricted materiality access represented challenges that motivated the infants to go further in their communicative attempts, facilitating distal and representational gestures. In this regard, planned educational action affects the gestures in the classroom and is necessary to maintain a balance between infants' needs and specific demands.

The results indicated that half of the infants' gestures were related to the activity of the teacher at the time of their occurrence. Besides, these productions were moderated by the planned educational action that established the potential communicative scenario. This implies that the teacher can influence how infants express themselves in the classroom, giving the adult a central role in the process of gesture development. Studies carried out with parents in family homes have reached similar conclusions (Basilio & Rodríguez, 2011, 2017; Cameron-Faulkner et al., 2015).

Immediate educational action provided indicators of the importance of the teacher in the process of acquisition and consolidation of gestures as a system of meaning. The teacher is responsible for: (1) promoting situations where infants can communicate freely and interact with materiality, (2) providing infants' gestures with a communicative value; and (3) being part of the specific process of gesture development by correcting the infants' productions, encouraging them to repeat their action or elaborate it.

Lock, Young, Service and Chandler (1990) concluded that infants do not develop gestures solely by imitation or repetition. Adults are models of referential frames in which the gesture can be used, but not models of the action itself. We relate the "correction" of the gestures by the teacher with this idea. When she departs from the infant's proposal, she provides relevance to the infant's gesture. She also generates a model of reference for the infant, giving him/her the opportunity to transform his/her own production into a more complex one in an environment of meaning. The imitation initiative comes from the teacher and not from the infant (Uzgiris, 1999), functioning as a model that is situated in the infant's zone of proximal development.

It is fundamental to point out the importance of analyzing gesture development in everyday life situations, like the Infant School, which is almost entirely absent in the psychological literature. In everyday situations, infants produce gestures in a meaningful way

and establish their own objectives within a context that makes sense for them, enabling the analysis of the functional aspects of the gestures.

Infant Schools, as well as family homes, are spaces that promote the bases of communication in infant development. Future research should contribute to establish decisive conclusions regarding: (1) the relation between infants' gestures, educational action and materiality; (2) a narrative of gesture development that accounts for the different ways of gesture acquisition; and (3) understanding the diversity of the educational action related to gesture development. We would recommend studying more educational centers and including the material 'proposal' offered by each school in the analysis.

We conclude that during the first year of life there is greater complexity in prelinguistic communicative development than that presented in previous literature. It is a challenge to continue the research on the early development of gestures, which could not only contribute to a greater knowledge about typical development, but also to the identification of indicators of early communicative difficulties (Benassi, 2012), and to the integration of programs of intervention for the promotion of early executive functions.

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THE EMERGENCE OF GESTURES IN THE FIRST YEAR OF LIFE IN THE INFANT SCHOOL CLASSROOM

Figures File

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

**Gestures that weren't directly related to immediate educational action*

Fig. 6